

Studies in Biheterocycles—Part V* : Mass Spectra of Some Formyl Derivatives of 2-(2'-Furyl) Indole and 2-(2'-Thienyl) Indole

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The mass spectral fragmentation patterns of 2-(2'-furyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde (Ia), 2-(2'-thienyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde (Ib), 2-[2'-(5'-formyl)furyl] indole-3-carboxaldehyde (IIa), 5-nitro-2-(2'-furyl)-indole-3-carboxaldehyde (IIIa) and 5-nitro-2-(2'-thienyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde (IIIb) are discussed. In all cases the molecular ion peak has been found to be the base peak. Formation of an ion corresponding to a 4-hydroxycarbazole derivative appears to be a characteristic fragmentation of these aldehydes.

THE mass spectra of unsymmetrical biheterocycles are of considerable interest as they may be complicated by rearrangement processes made possible by the proximity of the two heterocyclic rings. Recently we reported¹ the mass spectral fragmentation patterns of typical unsymmetrical biheterocycles viz., 2-(2'-furyl) indole (IVa), 2-(2'-thienyl)-indole (IVb) and their 5-nitro derivatives (Va-b). It was observed that many fragments undergo interesting rearrangements involving the neighbouring heterocyclic ring. The effect of the introduction of carboxylic and aldehydic groups into bipyridyl, on its mass spectral behaviour has been studied by Summers². This prompted us to study the effect of introduction of formyl group into these biheterocycles (IVa-b) (Va-b) on their mass spectral behaviour. During our investigations on electrophilic substitution reactions of biheterocycles³⁻⁵, we synthesized 2-(2'-furyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde (Ia), 2-(2'-thienyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde (Ib), 2-[2'-(5'-formyl)furyl] indole-3-carboxaldehyde (IIa), 5-nitro-2-(2'-furyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde (IIIa) and 5-nitro-2-(2'-thienyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde (IIIb) and mass spectral fragmentation pattern of these formyl derivatives is discussed in this paper.

The mass spectral data of (Ia) and (Ib) are given in Table 1. In both the cases the molecular ion peak is the base peak. In the case of the aldehyde (Ib) a half mass peak corresponding to the doubly charged molecular ion at m/e 113.5 is observed while in the case of (Ia) a half mass peak corresponding to the doubly charged molecular ion of 2-(2'-furyl) indole (IVa) is seen at m/e 91.5. The formation of most of the fragment ions in these compounds could be rationalized preliminarily by considering them as 2-heteroarylindole-3-carboxaldehydes. The presence of peaks at m/e 210, 182, 89 and 63 in the spectrum of the aldehyde (Ia) and peaks at m/e 226, 198, 89 and 63 in the spectrum of the aldehyde (Ib) could be attributed to the ions obtained by the successive loss of H radical, carbon

monoxide, ArCN (Ar=2-furyl or 2-thienyl) and acetylene from the respective molecular ions as shown in the Scheme 1. This type of fragmentation is a common feature of indole-3-carboxaldehydes⁶. Another fragmentation pathway is also observed involving the loss of carbon monoxide from the molecular ions of (Ia) and (Ib) to produce ions at m/e 183 and 199 respectively, corresponding to the molecular ions of indoles (IVa-b). These ions undergo further fragmentation to produce peaks at m/e 154, 153, 152, 127, 126, 91.5, 89, 77 and 63 in the spectrum of the aldehyde (Ia) and peaks at m/e 154, 127, 89, 77 and 63 in the spectrum of the aldehyde (Ib) as observed in the case of indoles (IVa) and (IVb) respectively. The high intensity peak at m/e 154 in both the spectra is attributed to a benzozapenta cation, which might have been formed by two fragmentation pathways. In one of the pathways the cations at m/e 182 and 198 may lose CO and CS respectively involving the neighbouring heterocyclic ring to give the ion at m/e 154. It may also result from the molecular ions of indoles (IVa-b) as reported earlier¹. The spectra of the aldehydes (Ia-b) show a common peak at m/e 183 which is attributed to the molecular ion of 4-hydroxycarbazole (VI), this probably arises by the rearrangement of the molecular ion followed by the loss of CS or CO. In the case of aldehyde (Ia) this peak also happens to be the molecular ion peak of 2-(2'-furyl) indole.

The mass spectral data of 2-[2'-(5'-formyl)furyl] indole-3-carboxaldehyde (IIa) are given in Table 1. The molecular ion peak at m/e 239 is the base peak. The peaks at m/e 211 and 183 are attributed to the molecular ions of aldehyde (Ia) and indole (IVa) respectively, which arise due to the loss of one and two molecules of carbon monoxide from the molecular ion of the dialdehyde (II). The peak at m/e 211 is also attributable to the molecular ion of 1-formyl-4-hydroxycarbazole (VII). The peaks at m/e 210, 183, 154, 153, 152, 128, 127, 126 and 101 which are observed in the

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TABLE 1

Mass spectral data of 2-(2'-furyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde (Ia), 2-(2'-thienyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde (Ib), 2-[2'-(5'-formyl) furyl] indole-3-carboxaldehyde(II), 5-nitro-2-(2'-furyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde (IIIa) and 5-nitro-2-(2'-thienyl) indole-3-carboxaldehyde (IIIb)

m/e (% abundance)*				
(Ia)	(Ib)	(IIa)	(IIIa)	(IIIb)
211 (100)	227 (100)	239 (100)	256 (100)	272 (100)
210 (46.7)	226 (52.5)	238 (48.7)	255 (17.6)	271 (36.7)
199 (4.0)	199 (21.7)	211 (8.0)	228 (4.8)	244 (4.2)
184 (3.3)	198 (5.8)	210 (16.0)	210 (14.4)	228 (20.8)
183 (22.0)	183 (10.0)	209 (2.0)	209 (19.2)	226 (8.3)
182 (6.0)	171 (11.7)	183 (10.0)	199 (4.8)	225 (25.0)
171 (3.3)	167 (5.9)	182 (21.3)	198 (14.4)	214 (3.3)
168 (2.0)	166 (4.2)	181 (2.0)	183 (9.6)	199 (4.2)
167 (2.7)	155 (2.5)	155 (8.7)	182 (30.4)	198 (20.8)
155 (12.0)	154 (13.3)	154 (36.0)	181 (9.6)	197 (6.7)
154 (46.7)	153 (3.3)	153 (8.7)	170 (5.6)	196 (10.0)
153 (5.3)	127 (4.2)	152 (2.7)	154 (24.0)	186 (3.3)
152 (2.0)	113.5 (8.3)	129 (2.0)	153 (16.8)	171 (10.8)
129 (2.3)	98.5 (2.9)	128 (10.0)	152 (6.4)	170 (2.5)
128 (8.0)	89 (4.2)	127 (14.0)	128 (11.2)	165 (2.5)
125 (6.0)	77 (2.5)	126 (8.7)	127 (19.2)	154 (9.2)
127 (11.3)	63 (5.0)	125 (2.7)	126 (16.0)	153 (4.2)
102 (2.0)	62 (2.5)	118 (2.0)	125 (3.2)	127 (4.2)
101 (4.7)	55 (4.2)	101 (8.0)	115 (3.2)	99 (2.5)
91.5 (9.3)	39 (3.7)	99 (2.0)	114 (2.4)	98.5 (5.8)
89 (4.7)	28 (33.3)	91.5 (2.0)	101 (5.6)	89 (4.2)
77 (5.3)	—	89.0 (4.0)	100 (2.4)	87 (5.8)
76 (2.0)	—	88 (3.3)	99 (3.2)	86 (4.2)
75 (4.0)	—	87 (2.0)	77 (5.6)	85.5 (4.2)
63 (4.7)	—	86 (2.0)	75 (12.0)	63 (6.7)
57 (4.0)	—	77 (11.3)	74 (6.4)	62 (6.7)
31 (4.7)	—	76.5 (2.0)	64 (4.0)	44 (4.2)
28 (28.7)	—	76 (2.7)	63 (19.2)	28 (12.5)
—	—	75 (6.7)	62 (6.4)	—
—	—	74 (3.3)	39 (16.0)	—
—	—	63 (8.7)	31 (40.0)	—
—	—	62 (4.0)	28 (56.0)	—
—	—	55 (3.3)	—	—
—	—	51 (5.3)	—	—
—	—	50 (4.7)	—	—
—	—	39 (6.7)	—	—
—	—	38 (2.0)	—	—
—	—	31 (8.7)	—	—
—	—	29 (4.0)	—	—
—	—	28 (23.3)	—	—

*Peaks with less than 2% intensity are not reported.

spectrum of the monoaldehyde (Ia) are also observed in the spectrum of the dialdehyde (IIa).

The mass spectral data of nitroaldehydes (IIIa-b) are also given in Table 1. The base peak is due to molecular ion at m/e 256 in the case of (IIIa) and at m/e 272 in the case of (IIIb). Loss of CO from each of these molecular ions results in the formation of ions at m/e 228 and at m/e 244 respectively, and are attributed to the respective molecular ions of nitroindoles (Va-b). Fragmentation of these ions in turn takes place as observed in the spectrum of nitroindoles earlier¹. The M-1 peak characteristic of aldehydes⁷ is also observed in both cases. The spectra of the nitroaldehydes (IIIa-b) show a common peak at m/e

228 which is attributed to the molecular ion of 4-hydroxy-6-nitrocarbazole (VIII). This peak also happens to be the molecular ion peak of 5-nitro-2-(2'-furyl) indole (Va) in the case of nitroaldehyde (IIIa).

From the above discussion it can be noticed that introduction of formyl group at position 3 of these biheterocycles results in the formation of a characteristic fragment ion corresponding to the respective 4-hydroxycarbazole which is formed probably by a rearrangement involving the neighbouring heterocycle before the α -cleavage of the molecular ion occurs. Except the above, the fragmentation of these aldehydes follows much the same pattern as that of indoles (IVa-b) and nitroindole (Va-b)¹.

Scheme 1

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The mass spectrum of these compounds were recorded on a Hitachi HMU-7L high resolution mass spectrometer.

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